

LINGUISTIC MEANS OF MODALITY EXPRESSION IN ENGLISH COMMUNICATION.

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ANOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola ingliz muloqot xulqida modallik ifodalanishining lingvistik vositalar yordamida qo'llanilishini yoritib bergan bo'lib, berilgan ma'lumotlar misollar yordamida asoslangan. Muloqot jarayonida e'tibor berilishi kerak bo'lgan modallikning ta'siriga alohida tasnif berilgan. Demak bu maqola ingliz madaniyati va muloqotiga qiziquvchilar uchun samarali bir ma'lumotlar to'plami bo'la oladi.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья проливает свет на использование языковых средств выражения модальности в английском коммуникативном поведении, а предоставленная информация основана на примерах. Отдельная классификация дана влиянию модальности, на которое следует обращать внимание в процессе общения. Таким образом, эта статья может стать эффективным сборником информации для тех, кто интересуется английской культурой и общением.

ANNOTATION

This article sheds light on the use of linguistic means of modality expression in English communication behavior, and the given information is based on examples. A separate classification is given to the influence of modality, which should be paid attention to in the process of communication. So this article can be an effective collection of information for those interested in English culture and communication.

Modal verbs express the action or state of the speaker through the infinitive represents the relationship. They are relative to the action expressed by the infinitive probability, obligation, necessity, advice, possibility, impossibility, doubt, serves to express an attitude such as distrust. Modal verbs: can (could), may (might), must, should, ought, shall, will, would, need, dare. Modals It is also expressed by to be + Infinitive and to have + Infinitive. Modal verbs It is also called defective (that is, defective), because there are many of them (from dare and need except) does not have a verb and analytical form. In addition, they are the third person -s is not added to the unit. Linked verb phrases are be able to,

have to, had better, used to, and be used to. Can has 2 forms: can is used for the present tense and could is used for the past tense.

- "I can't explain it," said Therese. "I can't explain anything I did today. "(Heim)"

"I can't explain it," said Therese. "I can't explain what I did today.

-He jumped as high as ever he could. (Galsworthy)

He jumped as high as he could.

Only present simple infinitive can is used in this sentence.

Probability

a) depending on the situation:

- I couldn't go to the theater yesterday because I was busy

I couldn't go to the theater yesterday because I was busy

In the last 3 sentences, can is close to may in the meaning of permission.

b) subject to the provisions of existing law:

- Every citizen can get medical treatment free of charge.

Every citizen has the right to medical treatment by the state.

You cannot play football in the street (i.e. you have no right).

You can't play football in the street (you don't have the right)

The simple infinitive can expresses probability.

Could is used in complimentary questions.

Could you give us a consultation tomorrow?

Can you advise us tomorrow?

Expresses doubt, surprise. (they are closely related). In such meanings, can is used with all forms of the infinitive in interrogative and negative sentences, although in interrogative sentences it expresses surprise. No wonder her father had hidden that photograph... But could he hate John's mother and yet keep her photograph? (Galsworthy) It's no wonder her dad covered up the picture. Even though he hated Johnny's mother, he still kept the picture. What did he find in that Bossini that made him lose his mind? Brett. They saw us. I hope they didn't recognize us. Geneva. The car was going too fast. They couldn't have seen us. (Gow and D'Usseau) Brett. He saw us. I hope they didn't recognize us. Geneva. The car was moving too fast. They could not see us. In the last 2 sentences, could and can can be interchanged without any change in meaning. The Perfect Infinitive with could has the same meaning as the Perfect Infinitive with can, except that it does not have the same category as can in the negative. If the action is in the past, the Perfect Infinitive is used. The use of other forms of the infinitive creates little difficulty. Use of the modal verb may might. The modal verb may has 2 forms: may for the present tense and might for the past tense.

The phrases to be allowed and to be permitted have the same meaning, they serve to provide the unmade form of may. "May I come along?" asked Karen. (Heim) "May I come to you?" asked Karen Jolyor thought he might not have the chance of saying it after. (Galsworthy) Jolyor thought that he would not have the opportunity to speak like that again. You are to stay in bed until you are allowed to get up. You must remain where you are until I give you permission. May is used to express the meanings of permission, distrust, probability, and lunging. Permission. "May I use your phone?" (Hey) May I use your phone? As noted, can is also used to express permission in a variety of ways: You may take the book means that the speaker is giving permission; You can take the book in this sentence there is no situation other than not taking the book. May expresses permission only with the present infinitive. Here we must emphasize the difference between permission and prohibition sentences. As long as the former is expressed by may, the latter can be expressed in other ways than may not. Answers to questions that mean asking for permission are also expressed by don't or must not.

May I read the letter?

May I read the letter?

- No, don't, please.

No, please don't do that

A bit stricter than don't may not, it is used to ask not to do something, rather than to order it to be done. The must not is not the person performing the action, but those facts, rules or criticizing the situation. You must not smoke so much
Uncertainty in the implementation of an action, situation, event:

- "You may think you're very old," he said, "but you strike me as extremely young." (Galsworthy)

Do you think you are old, he said, but you are too young for me you will be seen. In this case, we can see a small difference between may and might. Sometimes, might expresses the speaker's lack of confidence more strongly than may. Might is used instead of may in conjugation of tenses. That was like her — she had no foresight. Still — who knew? — she might be right. (Galsworthy) It looks like him - he couldn't sit looking ahead. Who knows? - maybe he is right. May is used with all forms of the infinitive to express uncertainty. A Forsyte might perhaps still be living in that house, to guard it jealously. (Galsworthy) Forsyte could guard that house and live in a frenzy. Probability depending on the situation. In this case, may is used only in indicative sentences. Can also be used in this case. In this museum you may see some interesting things. You can see interesting

things in the museum. You may see him every morning walking with his dog. You can find him walking his dog every morning. In this sense, it is usually expressed by the Indefinite Infinitive. Use of the modal verb must. The modal verb must has only one form. To have to and to be obliged to have the same meaning and are used in tenses where must cannot be used. Must represents obligation, necessity, important orders, lunging, trust. And now I must go back to my social duties. (Voinich) Now I must return to my duty. I felt that I had to have the air. (De la Roche) I felt I needed a change of air. Obligation, necessity. It depends on the situation (in this sense, it is equal to must to have to and it is expressed by the Indefinite Infinitive in interrogative, negative and demonstrative sentences):

- He must write. He must earn money. (London) He must write. He has to earn money.

The absence of necessity is expressed by need not:

b) for circumstances that have arisen in the human world and cannot be changed:

Compulsion or strong command. In this sense, it is usually used in the second and third persons and has a strong emphasis. Paula. I've got to tell Mr. Tanqueray. Hugh. By God, you shall do nothing of the sort Paula. I must tell Mr. Tenkery.

Hugh. I swear by Allah that you will not do that.

In interrogative sentences, shall expresses asking after prompts to the 1st and 3rd persons. The information given above was able to express only some units that represent modality in English communication behavior. We think that the above was able to show how special a place modality has in linguistics.

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